

Post-Interview Survey

Questions

1. Age:

- 18–24
- 25–34
- 35–44
- 45–54
- 55–64
- 65 and older
- Prefer not to say

2. Gender: *(Select all that apply)*

- Woman
- Man
- Transgender Woman
- Transgender Man
- Gender variant/ non-conforming/ non-binary
- Prefer to self-describe: _____
- Prefer not to say

3. What is your current role? *(e.g., Front-End developer, Project Manager, Back-End developer)*

4. In which country are you currently working? [list]

5. What is your country of origin? [list]

6. How many years of experience do you have as a software engineer?

- Less than 1 year
- 1 to 2 years
- 3 to 5 years
- 6 to 10 years
- Over 10 years

- Prefer not to say

7. Throughout your career as a software engineer, how many times have you changed jobs?

- Never
- 1–2 times
- 3–5 times
- More than 5 times
- Prefer not to say

8. What is the highest level of education you have completed?

- No formal education
- High school
- Technical training
- Undergraduate degree
- Master’s degree
- Doctorate degree (Ph.D)
- Prefer not to say

9. Are you currently employed in software engineering?

- Yes, full-time
- Yes, part-time
- No, but I was previously employed in software engineering
- No, I have never worked in software engineering
- Prefer not to say

10. Do you identify as belonging to any underrepresented group(s) in software engineering?

- Yes: _____
- No
- Prefer not to say